

Group Membership as a Predictor of Self-esteem and Perceived Discrimination in Indian Social Groups

Shraddhesh Kumar Tiwari

Post-Doctoral Fellow, Department of Psychology, Deen Dayal Upadhyay Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur (U.P.)

Arati Pandey

Associate Professor, Department of Psychology, B.R.D.B.D. P.G. College, Ashram Barhaj, Deoria (U.P.)

Dhananjay Kumar

Professor, Department of Psychology, Deen Dayal Upadhyay Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur (U.P.)

Abstract

This study was designed to address the relationship among implicit and explicit self-esteem and perceived discrimination in different social groups. 270 university students from different social group members (90 from each social group i.e., general category, other backward category and scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category) were administered perceived discrimination scale, explicit and implicit self-esteem scale. Obtained results reveal the social category wise relationship, in general category members, explicit self-esteem was negatively correlated with perceived discrimination. In other backward category members, implicit self-esteem Name, Surname and total were positively significant with perceived discrimination. In scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category members, Implicit self-esteem surname and implicit self-esteem total were negatively correlated with perceived discrimination. Discriminant function analysis yielded two functions in which first function separates SC/ST group from the other two groups namely General and OBC. The second discriminant function discriminates General category from OBC and SC/ST category. Overall findings documented the clear picture of Indian social categories. Findings were explained under social identity theories.

Keywords: Group membership, Implicit self-esteem, Explicit self-esteem, Perceived Discrimination, Discriminant function.

Introduction

Group membership is an important constituent of self-concept. People tend to evaluate their ingroup more favorably than other groups (Tajfel and Turner 1986). Social identity theory emphasizes ingroup favoritism among members of much different types of social groups (Hogg and Abrams 1988). People hold negative attitude towards the members of various groups but constitutional provision i.e., law, social pressure or fear of revenge serve to tend people from putting their prejudice view into open practice. Therefore, obvious form of discrimination is revealed as negative actions towards the objects of racial ethnic or religious practices (Swim and Stangor 1998).

Greenwald and Banaji (1995) differentiate the implicit and explicit self-esteem. Explicit self-esteem is based on conscious process, whereas, implicit self-esteem is result of automatic self-evaluative process. It reflects unconscious association with the self. They provide a second source of evidence supporting the presence of automatic evaluation of self-related objects. Research on Name Letter, mere ownership, and endowment effects indicate that people evaluate stimuli or objects associated with the self-more positively than comparable objects not associated with self. This effect demonstrated for letters in people's name (Hoorens & Nuttin, 1993) numbers in their birthday (Kitayama and Karasawa 1997), computer icons associated with the self (Feys, 1991), and a variety of physical objects that belong to self (Kahneman, Knetsch, and Thaler 1990).

An important impact on people's implicit self-evaluation is ethnicity. Research has found that members of stigmatized or low status groups sometime display subtle effect of their poor treatment by others. For example- low status group members often engage in outgroup

favoritism in comparison to high status group members (Jost and Banaji, 1994). Clark and Clark (1947) observed out group preference and negative self- stereotyping in African American children and similar result was found for Hispanic children (Bernat & Balch, 1979). People of colour can successfully deploy a number of strategies to protect their explicit self- evaluation (Crocker and Major, 1989), their implicit self- evaluation, especially their implicit group regard (the target of stereotypes), may still reflect the adverse effect of socially shared stereotypes (Hett and Pelham 2001). Members of many stigmatized groups (women, people of colors) often report that, whereas, their fellow in group members is frequently the target of discrimination, they themselves rarely feel the brunt of discrimination (Ruggiero & Taylor, 1995). Stigmatized group members often develop high self-esteem but findings also suggest that defending one's social identity against stigma and stereotypes may not be straightforward or consistently.

Indian society stratified as caste, class, gender, race and ethnicity. Caste and class are main theme of Indian society. Caste refers to hereditary and their rituals, class also indicate to occupation, social and economic status. Indian society is determined by birth and governed by customs, traditions and norms and values. An understanding of India's caste system and its evolution over time is necessary for the examination of caste-based discrimination (Khubchandani J, Soni A, Fahey N, et al. 2018). The aim of the study was to find out the relationship between self-esteem and perceived discrimination in three social category students.

Method

Participants: Random sampling was used to recruit 300 male college going students of three social categories (100 from General categories, 100 from Other Backward Categories, 100 from Scheduled Caste/ Scheduled Tribe Categories) from university and its affiliated colleges. The age range of subjects was 17 to 23 years with mean age 19.77.

Materials and procedure:

Three measures were used in this study.

Self Esteem Inventory (Coppersmith 1982): The inventory consists 25 items in English language. Reliability coefficient of English version tool was ranging from .71 to .80. Hindi adaptation of the scale was carried out by Tiwari, Patel and Kumar (2016) on three social categories students. The overall test-retest reliability coefficient was found to be .80($p < .01$).

Implicit Self-esteem: It was discovered by Josef Nutty Jr. (1985). In this study, participants name and surname alphabets were used jumbled randomly. Then, jumbled list of alphabets of Name and Surname were presented before subjects and instructed of aesthetic judgment of all alphabets of Name and Surname on a nine-point scale ranging not beautiful to extremely beautiful. The sum of the ratings on alphabets made by subjects was divided the total number of the alphabet of Name and Surname to get the score. The scoring of Name and Surname made separately. The score of name and surname constitutes the total score of implicit self-esteem. Thus, in the Name Letter Task scoring were made separately for Name and surname and total score of Implicit self-esteem.

Perceived Discrimination Questionnaire (Tiwari, Patel and Kumar 2017): It consists of 25 items of caste category related discrimination behaviour. The questionnaire was devised with four-point Likert type scale ranging strongly agree to strongly disagree. Questionnaire has good psychometric properties.

Results

Product moment correlation coefficients: In General category group, explicit self-esteem has negatively correlated with perceived discrimination ($r = -.286$, $p < .01$). A significant positive correlation has been found ($r = .242$, $p < .05$) between implicit self-esteem Name and implicit self-esteem Surname and with implicit self-esteem total ($r = .750$, $p < .01$). Implicit self-esteem Surname is also found to be significantly correlated ($r = .817$, $p < .01$) with implicit self-esteem total (Table 1).

Table 1: Correlation between self-esteem and perceived discrimination for general category

	Explicit Self esteem	Implicit Self-esteem Name	Implicit Self-esteem Surname	Implicit Self-esteem Total	Perceived Discrimination
Explicit Self esteem	1	.193	.079	.172	-.286**
Implicit Self-esteem Name		1	.242*	.750**	-.049
Implicit Self-esteem Surname			1	.817**	.022
Implicit Self-esteem Total				1	-.024
Perceived Discrimination					1

Note: ** (p<.01), *(p<.05)

In other backward category, explicit self-esteem has negatively correlated with implicit self-esteem surname ($r=-.227$, $p<.01$) and implicit self-esteem total ($r=-.201$, $p<.05$). Implicit self-esteem name and implicit self-esteem surname have positively correlated ($r=.375$, $p<.01$) and both are highly positively correlated (Implicit self-esteem Name $r=.775$, $p<.01$), (Implicit self-esteem Surname $r=.877$, $p<.01$) with implicit self-esteem total. Implicit self-esteem total has significantly correlated with perceived discrimination ($r=.239$, $p<.05$) (Table 2).

Table-2: Correlation matrix of Self Esteem and Perceived Discrimination in Other Backward Category

	Explicit Self-esteem	Implicit Self-esteem Name	Implicit Self-esteem Surname	Implicit Self-esteem Total	Perceived Discrimination
Explicit Self esteem	1	-.094	-.227*	-.201*	.082
Implicit Self-esteem Name		1	.375**	.773**	.201*
Implicit Self-esteem Surname			1	.877**	.201*
Implicit Self-esteem Total				1	.239*
Perceived Discrimination					1

Note: ** (p<.01), *(p<.05).

In SC/ST category, explicit self-esteem has not correlated with implicit self-esteem and perceived discrimination but implicit self-esteem surname ($r=-.216$, $p<.05$) and implicit self-esteem total ($r=-.234$, $p<.05$) have negatively correlated with perceived discrimination (Table 3).

Table-3: Correlation Matrix of Self Esteem and Perceived Discrimination for SC/ST Category

	Explicit Self Esteem	Implicit Self-esteem Name	Implicit Self-esteem Surname	Implicit Self-esteem Total	Perceived Discrimination
Explicit Self esteem	1	.025	-.030	-.018	-.151
Implicit Self-esteem Name		1	.424**	.741**	-.195
Implicit Self-esteem Surname			1	.911**	-.216*
Implicit Self-esteem Total				1	-.234*
Perceived Discrimination					1

Note: ** (p<.01), *(p<.05).

Discriminant Function Analysis:

A direct discriminant function analysis was performed. Three variables used as predictor of membership in three groups. Predictors were discrimination behaviour, explicit self-esteem, and implicit self-esteem. Groups were general category, other backward category and scheduled caste/ scheduled tribe category. There were 300 cases in which 100 for each category. There were no missing data in calculation.

Two discriminant function were calculated with combined $\chi^2(6) = 256.11 (p < .01)$, after removal of the first function, there was still strong association between groups and predictors $\chi^2(6) = 60.76 (p < .01)$. The two-discriminant function associated for 95.5% and 4.5% of the between group variability. As shown in figure (1) the first discrimination function separates SC/ST group from the other two groups namely General and OBC. The second discriminant function discriminates General category from OBC and SC/ST category. The loading matrix of correlation between predictors and discriminant functions as seen in suggest that the best predictors for distinguishing between SC/ST groups and other two groups are perceived discrimination. SC/ST group have perceived more discrimination ($M = 63.37$), than General ($M = 41.04$), and OBC ($M = 45.61$) groups.

Thus, the obtained results cleared that explicit self-esteem has negatively correlated with perceived discrimination in General category but, it is not correlated with perceived discrimination in OBC and SC/ST category. Implicit self-esteem has negatively correlated with perceived discrimination in SC/ST category and positively correlated with perceived discrimination in OBC. But it has not been correlated with perceived discrimination in General category. The obtained results confirmed that the discriminant function analysis yielded two functions: the first function separates SC/ST group from the other two groups namely General and OBC. The second discriminant function discriminates General category from OBC and SC/ST category. The predictors for distinguishing SC/ST group and other groups are perceived discrimination. Whereas, explicit self-esteem has emerged as the predictor to separate General category from OBC and SC/ST category.

Discussion

Obtained results confirms the negative significant association between explicit self-esteem and perceived discrimination for general category students. It means increased level of explicit self-esteem reversely reduce the perceived discrimination. On the other hands, in other backward category students' findings revealed a different pattern of association between self-esteem and perceived discrimination. All components of implicit self-esteem (Name, Surname

and Total implicit self-esteem) found positively correlated with perceived discrimination. Greenwald and Banaji (1995) defined implicit self-esteem as “the introspectively unidentified” effect of self-attitude on evaluation of self-associated and self-dissociated objects. On the level of processing, it is recognized as automatic or unconscious process and play a major role in almost all social psychological process (Bargh and Chartrand 1999). In scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category students, implicit self-esteem surname and implicit self-esteem total were found negative relationship with perceived discrimination. This pattern provides a picture of psychological mechanism of social group status in society. Included three social categories namely general category, other backward category and scheduled caste and scheduled tribe are a stratification of Indian social structure and it reflects the social and developmental status of social group or category. Establishment of these social caste/categories are consequence of a long struggle of social development and rights for under privilege people. Principles of caste refers to division of people into groups on the basis of birth and giving particular privilege to some group and denying similar privilege to others. The motive underlying caste system was racial and ethnic. Thus, negative relationship with perceived discrimination with implicit self-esteem surname and implicit self-esteem total confirms their correspondence to surname and self-associated objects. Studies on self-esteem and stereotypes on three social categories in India shows that scheduled caste /scheduled tribe category members manifested low self-esteem in comparison to general category and other backward category (Tiwari, Patel and Kumar 2017, Tiwari and Kumar 2014).

The discriminant function analysis yielded two functions; the first function separates SC/ST group from the other two groups namely General and OBC. The second discriminant function discriminates General category from OBC and SC/ST category. The predictors for distinguishing SC/ST group and other groups are perceived discrimination. Whereas, explicit self-esteem has emerged as the predictor to separate General category from OBC and SC/ST category. Obtained result also state that level of perceived discrimination is highest in SC/ST category in comparison to General and OBC category. Findings are also revealed that SC/ST category feels high perceived discrimination due to their caste, category and ethnicity. Studies on self-esteem suggest that healthy self-esteem is necessary for mental wellbeing and positive self-concept (Mayo Clinic 2009). Theories of self-esteem reveals the psychological mechanism of people’s mental health. Self-affirmation theory proposed that positive self-regard helps inoculate people against the stressors, strains and defeat of daily life (Taylor and Brown 1998). The terror management theory suggests that anxiety surrounding over awareness of our mortality intensifies our support of culturally shared belief system. In this articulation, feelings of self-esteem reflect the degree to which we believe we are meeting standard represented by our cultural world view. Thus, self-esteem buffers against the fear of death by connecting the self to meaning value and institutions that will preserve beyond individual life time (Pyszczynski, Greenberg and Solomon 1997).

Conclusion and Implications:

This study exposes the relationship between self-esteem and perceived discrimination in three social categories students, namely general category, other backward category and scheduled caste/scheduled tribe category. This study make enable to understand that general category explicit self-esteem and perceived discrimination negative relationship whereas both categories other backward category and SC/ST category denotes positive relationship between implicit self-esteem and perceived discrimination. However, explicit self-esteem has emerged as the predictor to separate General category from OBC and SC/ST category.

References :

- Bargh, J.A. & Chartrand, T.L. (1999). The unbearable automaticity of being. *American Psychologist*, 54, 462-479.
- Bernat, G., & Balch, P. (1979). The Chicano racial attitude measure: Result of an investigation. *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 7, 137-146.
- Clark, K.B., & Clark, M.P. (1947). Racial identification and preference in Negro children. In E.E. Maccoby, T.M. Newcomb, & E.L. Hartley (Eds.). *Reading in social psychology* (pp. 602-611). New York: Holt, Rinehart & Winston.
- Cooper Smith, S. (1982). *The antecedents of self-esteem*. Palo Alto, CA: Consulting Psychologists Press.
- Crocker, J. & Major, B. (1989). Social stigma and self-esteem: The self-protective properties of stigma. *Psychological Review*, 4, 608-630.
- Feys, J. (1991). Briefly induced belongingness to self and preference. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 21, 547-552.
- Greenwald, A.G. & Banaji, M.R. (1995). Implicit social cognition: Attitude, self-esteem and stereotypes. *Psychological Review*, 102, 4-27.
- Hett, J.J., & Pelham, W.B. (2001). A case for non-conscious self-concept. In G.B. Moskowitz (Ed.), *Cognitive social psychology: The Princeton symposium on the legacy and future of social cognition* (pp. 105-123). Washington D.C.: American Psychological Association.
- Hogg, M.A. & Abrams, D. (1988). *Social identification. A social psychology of intergroup relations and group processes*. London: Routledge.
- Hoorens, V., & Nuttin, J.M. (1993). Over evaluation of own attributes. More ownership or subjective frequency? *Social Cognition*, 11, 117-200.
- Jost, J.T. and Banaji, M.R. (1994). The role of stereotyping in system justification and the production of false consciousness. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 33, 1-27.
- Kahneman, D., Knetsch, J.L., & Thaler, R.H. (1990). Experimental test of the endowment effect and the Coase theorem. *Journal of Political Economy*, 98, 1325-1347.
- Khubchandani, J., Soni, A., Fahey, N. et al. Caste matters: perceived discrimination among women in rural India. *Arch Women's Mental Health* 21, 163-170 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00737-017-0790-1>
- Kitayama, S., & Karasawa, M. (1997). Implicit self-esteem in Japan: Name letters and birthday numbers. *Personality And Social Psychological Bulletin*, 23, 736-742.
- Mayo Clinic (2009). Self-esteem check: Too low, too high or just right? Retrieved February 1, 2009, from <http://www.mayoclinic.com/health/self-esteem/MH00128>.
- Nuttin, J.M.Jr. (1985). Narcissism beyond Gestalt and awareness: The name letter effect. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 15, 353-361.
- Psyszczynski, T., Greenberg, J., & Solomon, S. (1997). Why do we need what we need? A terror management perspective on the roots of human social motivation. *Psychological Inquiry*, 8, 1-20.
- Ruggiero, K.M. & Taylor, D.M. (1995). Coping with discrimination. How disadvantaged group members perceive the discrimination that confront them. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 68, 826-838.
- Swim, J.K. & Stangor, C. (1998). *Prejudice: The target's perspective*. Academic Press, San Diego, California.
- Tajfel, H., & Turner, J.C. (1986). The social identity theory of intergroup behaviour. In S. Worehel & W.G. Austin (Eds.). *The psychology of intergroup relations* (pp. 7-24). Chicago: Nelson Hall.
- Taylor, S.E. & Brown, J.D. (1998). Illusion and wellbeing: A social psychological perspective on mental health. *Psychological Bulletin*, 103, 193-210.
- Tiwari, S., Patel, A. and Kumar, D. (2017). Development of perceived discrimination questionnaire: A measure for different social categories students. *Journal of Psychological Research*, Vol. 12, No. 1, 81-88.
- Tiwari, S.K., Kumar, D. & Pandey, V. (2014). Group favouritism and perceived discrimination among students of different social categories. *International Journal of Education and Management Studies*, 4(2), 138-141.

